

Fate of contaminants of emerging concern in the Oslofjord: A model based analysis

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ABSTRACT

Six contaminants of emerging concern (CECs): clarithromycin, citalopram, tributylphosphate, benzotriazole, octocrylene and teflubenzuron, with differing sources, applications, and contrasting properties were selected for modeling their fate in the water column and the sediments of the Oslofjord. The FABM family models was used, which couples the benthic-pelagic model 2DBP with the biogeochemical model BROM and the elaborated contaminants transformation module. This approach parameterized processes of CECs partitioning with organic matter, and CECs decay due to biodegradation, photolysis, and hydrolysis. This combination of modules allows for the simulation of spatial and temporal variability of CECs during a period of intensive pollution and restoration. It was shown that: (i) the biological pump significantly affects transformations of CECs leading to seasonal variation of concentration in the water column; (ii) during the pollution period fluxes of particulate and dissolved matter are directed to the sediments; while there is a flux of dissolved CECs from the sediments; (iii) after cessation of the pollution a flux of dissolved CECs from the sediments was predicted for a certain period; (iv) properties of the CECs determine the effectiveness of the biological pump and duration of CECs existence in the water column and the sediments following the cessation of pollution.

1. Introduction

Chemicals are integral to everyone's daily life, but some are potentially harmful to the environment, including the marine environment. Among these chemicals, there are contaminants of emerging concern (hereafter CECs), whose presence in the environment has only recently begun to be investigated, and the potential effects of these substances on human health and biodiversity are often poorly characterized. The European Environment Agency (EEA) report on contaminants in European seas speaks of a large-scale contamination problem, caused mainly by synthetic chemicals and metals originating from human activities both on land and at sea (Andersen et al., 2019).

Understanding the fate of chemical substances in the coastal marine environment is therefore extremely important to ensure sustainable management of the natural ecosystem. These environments play a pivotal role in human society, through fisheries, leisure activities and commerce. However, the fate of contaminants will depend on multiple

complex processes, relating to the environmental conditions as well as the different chemical properties. Such processes will include: (i) CEC horizontal transport with currents and sinking with particles; (ii) CECs transformation, i.e. decomposition and partitioning with seasonally developing biota and organic matter (OM). The decomposition of CECs (biodegradation, hydrolysis, and photolysis) will depend on varying environmental factors (i.e., temperature, light, redox conditions). Therefore, understanding the fate of CECs is also dependent on our understanding of wider conditions in marine environment and their variability.

Modeling can provide a useful tool to gather quantitative estimates of the fate of CECs, under different environmental conditions and source scenarios. The application of models facilitates the testing of hypotheses about the processes that may be responsible for the observed distributions and variability. This is important in terms of predicted spatial and temporal variability of CECs, and to identify potential

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hot spots. Alongside observations, modeling can provide numerical estimates on the rates of transformation and fluxes. Understanding likely regions of accumulation in the water column or sea bed can also inform on the ultimate impact of CECs on the wider marine ecosystem.

For the Oslo fjord, a box model has previously been applied using a classical fugacity approach (Mackay, 2001). In addition, a parameterized exchange between water and sediment, water and air, and water and octanol was applied for 7 PCBs (polychlorinated biphenyls; Breivik et al. (2004)). However, seasonality in OM changes was not taken into account in this model. Accounting for the binding between pollutants and OM is very important as it recognizes the existence of a “biological pump” where a substance is partitioned between dissolved and particulate form, such that it can sink to the sediment. The importance of the biological pump as one of the major environmental sinks for pollutants was demonstrated in Dachs et al. (2002) and Nizzetto et al. (2010). The fluxes to the sediment are most apparent for hydrophobic substances where partitioning to sediments is a driver. Seasonal variability of OM production and destruction also play a major role as demonstrated for the partitioning of PCBs with OM by Daewel et al. (2020).

There may be important rearrangements of the vertical distributions of contaminants among particulate and dissolved phases of the surface waters, as about 98% of the global oceanic primary production is remineralized in the mesopelagic zone, and the degradation half-lives of many contaminants in water are much longer than those of OM (Daewel et al., 2020). In the open sea, this leads to the formation of maximum concentrations in subsurface waters, but in the coastal waters, it leads to accumulation of contaminants in the sediments.

The Oslo fjord, with a surface area of about 193 km² and maximum depth of about 100 m in the west and 150 m in the east, is a fairly enclosed waterbody, which is separated from the outer part of the fjord by a shallow 20 m sill. This restricts water circulation and greatly limits deep water exchange (Breivik et al., 2004). The fjord is located in the most densely populated area of Norway and receives input from two wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) situated on the eastern and western sides of the inner Oslofjord, as well as from several rivers that flow into it.

In this study, we conduct model-based analyses of the fate and distribution of selected CECs in the water column and sediments of the Oslo Fjord. We evaluate scenarios representing present-day pollution levels as well as potential restoration efforts using a one-dimensional coupled benthic-pelagic model. For this purpose, we apply the Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models (FABM; Bruggeman and Bolding (2014)), which enables efficient coupling of a hydrodynamic host model with biogeochemical and matter transformation modules. The specific objective of this work is to develop a set of FABM-compatible modules to simulate the fate of CECs in the marine environment. These modules will parameterize the degradation of CECs via hydrolysis, photolysis, and biodegradation, as well as their partitioning with organic matter.

2. Methods

CECs can come from a wide range of applications, such as plastic additives, pharmaceuticals, personal-care products, pesticides and biocides to name just a few. There are estimated to be more than 350,000 chemicals on the market, with around 100,000 used within the European Union (EU; Wang et al. (2020)). The list of potential CECs is therefore very large and it is clearly not feasible to model all of them. Therefore, 6 illustrative CECs (iCECs) were chosen here, with selection based on the desire to capture a range of substances with differing sources, applications and properties that will influence their fate when they enter the marine environment. This list consists of:

- Clarithromycin (CAS 81103-11-9): a pharmaceutical and macrolide antibiotic, expected to be discharged via municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluents;

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the Bottom RedOx Model (BROM). The biogeochemical processes include transformations of O₂, N, Mn, Fe, S, C, and P. The ecosystem is represented by autotrophs, heterotrophs, and both heterotrophic and autotrophic bacteria under oxic and anoxic conditions. The model domain encompasses the water column, the Bottom Boundary Layer, and the upper sediments. See details in Yakushev et al. (2017).

- Citalopram (CAS 59729-33-8): a pharmaceutical, expected to be discharged via WWTP effluents;
- Tributylphosphate (CAS 126-73-8): a polymer additive and pH regulator with numerous application areas, expected to be discharged via WWTP effluents, coastal runoff, and air;
- Benzotriazole (CAS 95-14-7): has widespread use in numerous application areas including products for lubrication, washing and coatings, expected to be discharged via WWTP effluents and coastal runoff;
- Octocrylene (CAS 6197-30-4): a UV-stabilizer and ingredient used for protection of products from damage via sunlight, expected to be discharged via WWTP effluents and direct coastal runoff;
- Teflubenzuron (CAS 83121-18-0): benzoylurea insecticide, expected to be discharged with runoff and via applications in animal health including coastal fish farms.

These 6 chemicals cover a wide range of physicochemical properties and expected fate in the environment, including varying partitioning coefficients, K_{OW} (from 10¹ to 10⁶; Table 1), differing potential for biodegradability, and different rates of hydrolysis and photolysis (with half-life times changing from hours to hundreds of years). This diversity of iCECs provides an opportunity to investigate the range of fates that may be expected across the vast array of CECs that may potentially enter coastal waters.

To simulate the fate of the iCECs, we must predict their transport and transformation processes, such as decomposition via hydrolysis and potential interaction with OM. We used the 2-Dimensional Benthic Pelagic transport model (2DBP) coupled with the biogeochemical Bottom RedOx Model (BROM) and a newly developed iCEC transformation module. The iCECs transformation module parameterizes partitioning of iCECs with seasonally developing biota and OM (predicted by BROM), processes of iCECs decomposition (biodegradation, hydrolysis, and photolysis), and influence of environmental factors (i.e. temperature, light, redox conditions). The modules are coupled using the Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models, FABM (Bruggeman and Bolding, 2014) (see Fig. 1).

To simulate the change of concentration, C_i , of a component (e.g., contaminants, forms of nutrients, and biological organisms) with time, considerations of the model include advective transports (second term

in Eq. (1)), the turbulent diffusion (third term in Eq. (1)), biogeochemical/pollutant sink/source terms, R_{C_i} , and sinking (the last term in Eq. (1)):

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + \nabla C_i \vec{V} - \nabla(K \nabla C_i) = R_{C_i} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(w_{C_i} C_i) \quad (1)$$

where \vec{V} is the current velocity, K is the eddy diffusion coefficient, and w_{C_i} is the sinking rate, which is zero for dissolved parameters (i.e., pollutants, nutrients in the dissolved phase) and different from zero for the living organisms, detritus and contaminants partitioned with them.

2.1. Transport model

The 2-Dimensional Benthic-Pelagic model (2DBP) is designed to simulate the vertical and horizontal transport of both particulate and dissolved substances in the water column and the upper layers of the sediments, with a focus on small-scale horizontal spatial domains (Yakushev et al., 2020). In this study, we use a one-dimensional vertical approach, focusing on vertical variations in the water column and sediments while disregarding horizontal differences. Vertical grid resolution varies from tens to single units of meters. In the sediments, the model vertical resolution increased from 100 μm near the Sediment Water Interface (SWI) to 2 cm in the deeper layers.

The parameterized vertical transport mechanisms include vertical diffusivity and particulate matter sinking. For the water column vertical diffusivity, the General Ocean Turbulence Model (GOTM; Umlauf et al. (2005)) parameterization is used. Vertical diffusivity is estimated with the Gargett approach (Gargett, 1984). 2DBP is forced by output from the FjordOS hydrodynamic model (Staalström and Røed, 2016), which is an application of the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS; Haidvogel et al. (2008)), with the domain covering the entire Oslo fjord. This output provides climatology of the seasonal variability of temperature, salinity, irradiance and current velocity for the central part of the Western Oslofjord.

2.2. Biogeochemical model

The aim of the biogeochemical module is to parameterize the seasonality of the production and destruction of OM, its oxidation in oxic and anoxic conditions and interaction between the cycles of several chemical elements.

A schematic diagram of the considered variables of the BROM biogeochemical processes is shown in Figure. The model is described in detail in Yakushev et al. (2017). The predicted formation, transport and decay of OM in the water and in the sediments were used as a background for parameterization of processes of partitioning of iCECs.

2.3. Contaminant transformation model

2.3.1. Model components

We assumed that contaminants were partitioned between the free dissolved fraction (C_{Free}) and the fractions associated with phytoplankton and bacteria (C_{PHY}), heterotrophs (C_{HET}), particulate OM (C_{POM}) and dissolved OM (C_{DOM}). The fractions of contaminants partitioned with living organisms and detritus undergo vertical transport in association with the sinking material (Fig. 2); therefore, they have the same sinking rate as the material they are associated with.

Table 1

Literature estimates of octanol–water partitioning coefficients K_{OW} applied in the model partitioning coefficients.

Contaminant	Log K_{OW}	K_{OW} , L/kg
Clarithromycin	3.2 ^a	1500
Citalopram	3.5 ^b	3100
Tributylphosphate	4 ^c	10 000
Benzotriazole	1.3 ^d	20
Octocrylene	6.1 ^e	1 250 000
Teflubenzuron	5.0 ^f	100 000

^a Drugbank (2025b).

^b Drugbank (2025a).

^c OECD (2002).

^d ECHA (2023a).

^e ECHA (2024a).

^f ECHA (2023c).

2.3.2. Contaminants partitioning model

As the focus of our study is to track particularly interesting contamination gradients emerging from the interaction of iCECs with marine OM, we considered CECs with different hydrophobic properties, persistence and potential for bioaccumulation. Hydrophobic chemicals that are present in the water column partition between water phase, dissolved OM (DOM) and particulate OM (POM), and with living organisms (Fig. 2). Partitioning is a function of temperature, compound-specific physical–chemical properties, and characteristics of OM (Schwarzenbach et al., 2016). For the selected iCECs, there is only data of octanol–water partitioning coefficients (Table 1), that were assumed to also apply for the partitioning between living organisms and particulate and dissolved OM.

As a first approximation, the partitioning among these phases can be considered instantaneous (Mackay, 2001). This concept is based on the assumption that a high surface/volume ratio of microscale particles (such as phytoplankton) or nano to sub-nano scale DOM largely reduces the time to reach diffusive equilibrium. Following Daewel et al. (2020), the K_{OW} values (Table 1) are used as proxies for partitioning of contaminants between the dissolved phase and the organic matter associated with biota, POM, and DOM. The partitioning of these substances with OM is considered to be a fast process, and the parts of the different CEC-bonded compartments were calculated with the following system of equations during each time step:

$$C_{Free} = \frac{V_{Free}(C_{PHY} + C_{HET} + C_{POM} + C_{DOM})}{V_{Free} + K_{BW}V_{PHY} + K_{BW}V_{HET} + K_{PW}V_{POM} + K_{DW}V_{DOM}} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{PHY} = \frac{K_{BW}C_{Free}V_{PHY}}{V_{Free}} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{HET} = \frac{K_{BW}C_{Free}V_{HET}}{V_{Free}} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{POM} = \frac{K_{PW}C_{Free}V_{POM}}{V_{Free}} \quad (5)$$

$$C_{DOM} = \frac{K_{DW}C_{Free}V_{DOM}}{V_{Free}} \quad (6)$$

where C_{PHY} , C_{HET} , C_{POM} , C_{DOM} and C_{Free} are concentrations of the contaminants that are associated with biota (phytoplankton or bacteria and heterotrophs), POM, DOM and the water-dissolved phase, respectively; V_{PHY} , V_{HET} , V_{POM} and V_{DOM} represent the volumes that are occupied by biota, POM, and DOM per water volume ($V_{tot} = 1\text{L}$); $V_{Free} = V_{tot} - V_{PHY} - V_{HET} - V_{POM} - V_{DOM}$; K_{BW} , K_{PW} and K_{DW} are the equilibrium partitioning coefficients for the biota/water, POM/water, and DOM/water systems, respectively. This approach for the phase distribution parameterization differs from that used in cases where only POM was considered as applied, e.g., in Ilyina et al. (2006) and O'Driscoll et al. (2011).

The process of pollutant sorption on organic material in a marine environment depends on many factors such as the organic content

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of partitioning of a selected contaminant with state variables of the BROM model (shown in red) and processes of contaminants decomposition: degradation, photolysis, and hydrolysis. It is assumed that the total pollutant can be partitioned between contaminant (C_{PHY}) in phytoplankton and bacteria (PHY, Bact), contaminant (C_{HET}) in heterotrophs (HET), contaminant (C_{POM}) in particulate OM (POM-I, POM-sl), contaminant (C_{DOM}) in dissolved OM (DOM-I, DOM-sl), and remaining free dissolved fraction (C_{Free}). Partitioned with particulate matter contaminants sink with the sinking speed of corresponding particles. Decomposition can be affected by light, pH and oxygen conditions.

and composition of adsorbing matrices, the chemical structure of a contaminant, and the lipid fraction in living organisms (Schwarzenbach et al., 2016; Mackay, 2001). A number of different parameterizations of K_{BW} , K_{PW} and K_{DW} have been reported in the literature both from controlled laboratory studies and field monitoring, with a variance ranging across orders of magnitude (Table 1 and references). In addition, no explicit parameterizations are available for K_{BW} and K_{PW} for phytoplankton, so a simplified functional relationship was chosen to the known value of K_{OW} (Table 1).

2.3.3. Contaminants decay model

The process of contaminants degradation is complicated and varies from one congener to another (Mackay, 2001). A number of processes simultaneously occur, resulting in a decrease in the contaminant concentration, including hydrolysis, photolysis, or biodegradation (Mackay, 2001). Rates of these processes were parameterized as first-order equations:

$$R_i^H = K_H f(pH) C_i \quad (7)$$

for hydrolysis rate R_i^H with hydrolysis rate coefficient K_H and dependence on pH $f(pH)$

$$R_i^P = K_P f(I) C_i \quad (8)$$

for photolysis rate R_i^P with photolysis rate coefficient K_P and dependence on light conditions $f(I)$.

$$R_i^D = K_D f(O_2) C_i \quad (9)$$

for biodegradation rate R_i^D with biodegradation rate coefficient K_D and dependence on redox conditions $f(O_2)$. Available estimates for K_H , K_P and K_D are given in Table 2.

Total contaminant decomposition rates R_i , where i denotes the specific contaminant, account for the biodegradation of all contaminant forms in the model. Photolysis is considered only for dissolved forms, while hydrolysis is limited to the dissolved free form:

$$R_{C_{DIS}} = (K_D f_{ox}(O_2) + K_P f_I(I_z) + K_H) f_i(t) C_{DIS} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{C_{PHY}} = K_D f_{ox}(O_2) f_i(t) C_{PHY} \quad (11)$$

$$R_{C_{HET}} = K_D f_{ox}(O_2) f_i(t) C_{HET} \quad (12)$$

$$R_{C_{POM}} = K_D f_{ox}(O_2) f_i(t) C_{POM} \quad (13)$$

$$R_{C_{DOM}} = (K_D f_{ox}(O_2) + K_P f_I(I_z)) f_i(t) C_{DOM} \quad (14)$$

where $f(I)$ is the dependence on light:

$$f_I(I_z) = \frac{I_z}{I_{opt}} \exp\left(1 - \frac{I_z}{I_{opt}}\right) \quad (15)$$

that describes also photoinhibition and considers optimal (I_{opt}) and depth specific (I_z) light intensity.

The changes between the process rates occurring in oxic and suboxic conditions were parameterized with “soft switch” based on hyperbolic tangents

$$f_{ox}(O_2) = 0.5 + 0.5 \tanh(O_2 - O_2^{subox}) \quad (16)$$

where O_2^{subox} is the threshold oxygen concentration at which the changes occur, and O_2 is the dissolved oxygen concentration.

To parameterize the influence of temperature on the rates of the CECs decomposition, we used the temperature coefficient (Q_{10}) function, showing the enhancement effect of temperature on scaled physiological processes. It is assumed that all processes are regulated by ambient temperature and utilize the same Q_{10} value, which is the factor by which the rate of a reaction (R) increases for every 10-degree rise in temperature. Following Blackford et al. (2004), we mimic enzyme inhibition at high temperatures that are needed to prevent excessive reaction rates at higher temperatures:

$$f_i(t) = Q_{10}^{\frac{t-10}{10}} - Q_{10}^{\frac{t-32}{3}} \quad (17)$$

where t is the water temperature in degrees Celsius, $Q_{10} = 2$, and $f_i(t)$ represents the temperature rate dependence (see Fig. 3).

2.4. Oslo fjord biogeochemical model setup

The BROM coupled with 1-dimensional version of 2DBP, was applied for the Oslo fjord, aiming to simulated the changes in the biogeochemical regime during the last decades (Staalström et al., 2024).

The BROM-2DBP model considered the seasonal influence of hydrodynamical characteristics (temperature, salinity, mixing, light) and a source of OM discharging from WWTPs. The model was spun up for 100 model years from vertically homogeneous initial conditions with repeated year forcing and boundary conditions until the model had reached an approximately steady state of variability (Fig. B.18). The model parameters were “tuned” while running multiple spin-ups to ensure the model reproduced the spatial and temporal dynamics of

Table 2

Available estimates of the half-life time and assumed model rates of contaminants decay due to hydrolysis (K_H), photolysis (K_p) and biodegradation (K_D).

Contaminant	Hydrolysis Half life time and K_H	Photolysis Half life time and K_p	Biodegradation Half life time and K_D
Clarithromycin	3.5 - 365 days ^a $K_H = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$	0.15 days ^b $K_p = 4.66 \text{ d}^{-1}$	3.5 - 365 days ^a $K_D = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$
Citalopram	Nil ^c $K_H = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$	28 days ^d $K_H = 0.024 \text{ d}^{-1}$	3.5 - 365 days ^a $K_D = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$
Tributylphosphate	11.45 years ^a $K_H = 0.00019 \text{ d}^{-1}$	Not estimated ^e $K_p = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$	<7 days ^e $K_D = 0.099 \text{ d}^{-1}$
Benzotriazole	1050 days ^f $K_H = 0.00066 \text{ d}^{-1}$	14–28 days ^e $K_p = 0.024 \text{ d}^{-1}$	831 days ^f $K_D = 0.00083 \text{ d}^{-1}$
Octocrylene	206 years ⁱ $K_H = 0.000001 \text{ d}^{-1}$	33 days ^j $K_p = 0.021 \text{ d}^{-1}$	>180 days ⁱ $K_D = 0.0039 \text{ d}^{-1}$
Teflubenzuron	30 days ^l $K_H = 0.023 \text{ d}^{-1}$	20 days ⁿ $K_p =$ 0.035 d^{-1}	115–170 days ^m $K_D = 0.0041 \text{ d}^{-1}$

a-United States Environmental Protection Agency (2025); b-Rodríguez-López et al. (2021b); c-ECHA (2023b); d-Jiménez-Holgado et al. (2021); e-ECHA (2024b); f-ECHA (2023a); g-Janssen et al. (2015); h-Liu et al. (2013a); i-ECHA (2024a); j-O'Malley et al. (2021); k-Liu et al. (2013b); l-Scheepmaker (2008); m-Calicide (1999); n-Marsella et al. (2000).

Fig. 3. Dependence of the CECs decomposition rates on temperature normalized to temperature 20 °C.

simulated variables as close as possible to the observed dynamics (see Fig. B.19). The details of the spatial and seasonal variability of the BROM model variables and comparison with the observations data are presented in Staalstrøm et al. (2024).

2.5. iCEC contamination scenarios

To analyze the transformations of the 6 selected iCECs in the water column and the upper sediment layers, we made calculations for 21-year dynamics with the following scenario:

- year 1 (year 2014 in Figures below): no pollution,
- years 2–11 (years 2015–2024 in Figures below): pollution with a discharge in the upper water layer,
- years 12–21 (years 2025–2035 in Figures below): no pollution.

This scenario allowed us to analyze the distribution and seasonal variability of iCECs during the period of pollution, and in the period of restoration, after the potential cessation of pollution.

To parameterize iCEC discharges, we used estimates of the wastewater discharge rates from municipal treatment plants, and data on iCECs concentrations in treated wastewater from these plants (Table 3). The discharge rate of treated wastewater in the Oslo region is approximately

3500 L/s from VEAS wastewater treatment plant (located in Asker), and about 2500 L/s from Bekkelaget wastewater treatment plant (located in Oslo East; COWI (2018)). These numbers vary considerably depending on rainfall etc, but these are good approximations of the order of magnitude.

Therefore, in the model, the rates of the iCEC discharges during the pollution period were assumed to be constant and equal, correspondingly,

- 144 µg/s for clarithromycin,
- 576 µg/s for citalopram,
- 192 µg/s for tributylphosphate,
- 2790 µg/s for benzotriazole,
- 1614 µg/s for octocrylene,
- Unknown for teflubenzuron.

Unfortunately, no analysis has been performed for teflubenzuron in relation to wastewater treatment plants, so its discharge was selected as the best fit for the calculated distributions (see below in Results). In the model, these iCECs discharge rates were divided by the volume of the water of the upper 5 m thick layer of the Oslofjord with a square of about 400 km², to estimate the changes of the iCECs concentrations.

Fig. 4. Modeled seasonal variability in the Oslo fjord of the selected variables of the model BROM: T - temperature, S - sulfur, O₂ - dissolved oxygen, PHY - phytoplankton, HET - heterotrophs, POM - particulate organic matter, NO₃ - nitrate, PO₄ - phosphate, Si - silicon, DOM - dissolved organic matter, NH₄ - ammonia, NO₂ - nitrite (Yakushev et al., 2017). The upper plots show the vertical distribution in the 90-meter water column, and the bottom plots show distributions at SWI, with 10 cm in bottom water and 10 cm in the sediment.

3. Results

3.1. Water column and sediment biogeochemistry

Modeled seasonal variability of hydrophysical and biogeochemical characteristics, including living organisms and POM is presented in Fig. 4. Parameters characterizing redox changes are shown in Fig. B.21. Simulations using the hydrodynamic model ROMS show an increase in temperature from April to September. The thermocline, which forms in April, deepens throughout the summer and autumn, and generally breaks down by December-January. During the summer, a decrease in salinity is observed, attributed to freshwater coastal runoff.

The biogeochemical model satisfactorily reproduced general features of seasonal changes of biota and biogeochemical characteristics of the water column and upper sediment. The simulated PHY concentrations from 0 to 1.9 $\mu\text{M N}$ (these model's units correspond to 0-7.0 $\mu\text{g Chl-a/L}$) are close to observed ones 0-5.4 $\mu\text{g Chl-a/L}$ (Staalström et al., 2024). The modeled HET maximum of 0.8 $\mu\text{M N}$ would correspond to 1100 mg WW/m^3 , assuming a nitrogen content of 1% of the wet weight zooplankton biomass (Menden-Deuer and Lessard, 2000). The model results for biogeochemistry were compared with the observed distributions of dissolved oxygen and nutrients (Fig. B.19), the data that is available for the Oslo fjord after last decade monitoring studies (Staalström et al., 2024) and also data from the databases i.e. Garcia et al. (2019).

The April–June phytoplankton bloom depletes inorganic nutrients from the upper 20 m layer and makes the surface water above the seasonal pycnocline nutrient-poor for the vegetation period. The phytoplankton is intensively consumed by HET in May–July. The seasonal ecosystem cycle is closed by the winter convective mixing combined with a substantial reduction of insulation.

Particulate organic matter (POM) produced in the water column during the vegetation period sinks and accumulates at SWI, where it decomposes, consuming oxygen from the bottom layer and releasing nutrients. The buried organic matter in the sediments is primarily mineralized by oxygen and nitrate, but also by oxidized forms of iron and manganese, leading to reduced concentrations of these oxidized forms in summer compared to winter. In the deeper sediment layers, an increase in the concentrations of reduced forms of iron and manganese, as well as ammonia and hydrogen sulfide, is predicted. A distinctive

feature of BROM is its parameterized dependence of the burial rate on the flux of particulate matter to the seafloor (Yakushev et al., 2017), which enables the prediction of seasonal variations in burial rates. In the Oslofjord, the modeled burial rate ranges from 4 to 8 mm/year , consistent with observational data (Papadopoulos and Stratigraphy, 2020).

Therefore the model reproduces the mechanism of the biological pump leading to the transport of nutrients from the upper layers of the water column to the sediments and the consequent burying. This parameterized mechanism was used as a biogeochemical baseline scenario for iCECs fate analysis.

Some more details of the spatial and temporal variability of the BROM model variables in the water column and the sediments are given in the Appendix B.

3.2. Temporal distribution of iCECs modeling

The measured concentration of iCECs in different environmental matrices is given in Table 4. These values were used for the model calibration. The discharge rates and the rates of partitioning and decomposition of the CECs were altered within the maximum possible limits (Tables 1, 2) to ensure a better correspondence with the observed concentrations.

3.2.1. Benzotriazole

The modeled concentrations of benzotriazole are comparable with the observed measurements and laboratory analyses (Table 4),

- 0–10 ng/L modeled and 0.9–2.9 ng/L observed for the sea water,
- 0–50 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ modeled and <50 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ observed for the sediments, and
- 0–200 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ modeled and <0.5 - 850 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ observed for biota

Benzotriazole is a relatively mobile substance. The model suggests that concentrations of benzotriazole in the water column are affected by the biological pump. Synthesis of OM during the vegetation period leads to accumulation of benzotriazole in particles which then sink. This leads to a decrease of the dissolved benzotriazole concentrations in water in summer. In the winter period, concentrations of the dissolved benzotriazole increase (Fig. 5).

Table 3

Measured concentrations of the contaminants in treated wastewater discharges to Oslofjord according to the Norwegian Environment Agency database “vanmiljø” available at <https://vanmiljo.miljodirektoratet.no/>.

Contaminant	Average, ng/L	Median, ng/L	Minimum, ng/L	Maximum, ng/L	Analyses No
Clarithromycin	41	24	0.2	180	30
Citalopram	113	96	0.3	380	30
Tributylphosphate	76	32	0.07	1300	56
Benzotriazole	1024	465	7	3400	30
Octocrylene	1949	269	3	13 000	40
Teflubenzuron	–	–	–	–	–

Table 4

Observed concentrations of iCECs in the Norwegian environment as reported in the Norwegian Environment Agency database “vanmiljø” available at <https://vanmiljo.miljodirektoratet.no/>.

Contaminant	Marine water (ng/L)	Marine sediment (ng/g DW)	Marine biota (ng/g WW)	Freshwater (ng/L)	Freshwater sediment (ng/g DW)	Freshwater biota (ng/g WW)
Clarithromycin	<10	<2.6	<0.04–0.62	<0.2–0.9	<0.9–2.4	<0.04–0.64
Citalopram	–	<1.5–0.4	<0.1–1.0	0.06–23	<1.4–0.3	<0.06–9.5
Tributylphosphate	5.6–42.0	0.1–532	0.02–737	0.07–3396	0.3–4300	0.09–109
Benzotriazole	0.9–2.9 ^a	<50	<0.5–850	<5.7–361	<12	<0.5–450
Octocrylene	–	<6–260	<0.2–2103	<1–800	<0.7–2200	<0.2–36
Teflubenzuron	<1.0–12.9	<0.05–269	<0.2–186	–	–	<0.05–0.8

^a No data from Norwegian database available. Data from NORMAN EMPODAT database was used (NORMAN, 2023).

Fig. 5. Seasonal and interannual changes of benzotriazole during the 21-year scenario. Where $C_{tot,diss}$ ($ng L^{-1}$) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, $C_{tot,part}$ ($ng L^{-1}$) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, $C_{in,biota}$ ($\mu g kg^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{tot,hydrolysis}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{tot,photolysis}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{tot,biodegrad}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $1395 \mu g/s$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 20$, $k_H = 0.00066 d^{-1}$, $K_P = 0.024 d^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00083 d^{-1}$. In this figure and below the upper plots show the vertical distribution in the 90-meter water column, and the bottom plots show distributions at SWI, with 10 cm in bottom water and 10 cm in the sediment.

During the 5 first years of the pollution period in the modeling scenario (2016–2020 in Fig. 6), the fluxes at the SWI of dissolved and particulate contaminants were predominantly directed to the sediment. In the following years, an equilibrium was reached, with seasonal but no interannual changes. After the modeled cessation of the pollution at the end of 2026, the concentrations in the upper layers of the water column decreased to zero, while the concentrations in the bottom layer remained detectable due to re-mobilization from the sediments. The downward flux of particulate benzotriazole stopped, but the upward flux of dissolved benzotriazole from the sediments to the lower layers of the water column continued.

3.2.2. Octocrylene

Octocrylene is a highly lipophilic substance. This is reflected in the trends observed in the modeling scenario (see Fig. 7, Fig. 8). The substance partitions heavily towards sediments and particulate matter, and the levels observed in the water column reflect the particulate load and proximity to the bottom sediments. According to the model assumption (Table 2) removal of octocrylene from the system is predicted to be dominated by photolysis in the upper levels of the water column, and to a limited extent by biodegradation (Jentzsch et al., 2019). Levels of octocrylene are predicted to remain many years after the cessation of a pollution period. The downward flux of particulate

Fig. 6. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of benzotriazole (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) at SWI during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved benzotriazole, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound benzotriazole. Constant injection with a rate of $1395 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 20$, $k_H = 0.00066 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_p = 0.024 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00083 \text{ d}^{-1}$.

Fig. 7. Seasonal and interannual changes of octocrylene during the 21-year scenario. Where $C_{\text{tot_diss}}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, $C_{\text{tot_part}}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, $C_{\text{in_biota}}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{\text{tot_hydrolysis}}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{\text{tot_photolysis}}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{\text{tot_biodegrad}}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $8 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 1250000$, $K_H = 0.000001 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_p = 0.021 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.0039 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The vertical distribution is presented as described in Fig. 5.

Fig. 8. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of octocrylene (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) at SWI during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved octocrylene, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound octocrylene. Constant injection with a rate of $8 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 1250000$, $K_H = 0.000001 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_p = 0.021 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.0039 \text{ d}^{-1}$.

Fig. 9. Seasonal and interannual changes of clarithromycin during the 21-year scenario. Where $C_{i_tot_diss}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, $C_{i_tot_part}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, $C_{i_in_biota}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{i_tot_hydrolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{i_tot_photolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{i_tot_biodegrad}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $70 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 1500$, $K_H = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_P = 4.66 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The vertical distribution is presented as described in Fig. 5.

Fig. 10. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of clarithromycin (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) at SWI during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved clarithromycin, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound clarithromycin. Constant injection with a rate of $70 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 1500$, $K_H = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_P = 4.66 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$.

octocrylene stops, but the upward flux of remobilized substance from the sediments to the lower layers of the water column continues, albeit limited by high lipophilicity. In some studies, octocrylene is claimed to be photostable (Duis et al., 2022), in this case the pollution of the sediments should be higher.

Modeled concentrations of octocrylene compared well with laboratory analyses (Table 4).

- 0–0.03 ng/L modeled and pg/L levels or below detection limits observed,
- 0–300 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW modeled and <6 - 260 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW observed for the sediments, and
- 0–1500 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW modeled and <0.2 - 2103 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW observed for biota

3.2.3. Clarithromycin

Clarithromycin has a moderate lipophilicity ($\text{Log } K_{OW} 3.2$). Photolysis is indicated as the fastest route for removal of the substance with a documented half-life of 0.15 days (Table 2). This is reflected in the scale of removal of clarithromycin by this route compared to that of hydrolysis and biodegradation in Fig. 9, Fig. 10. Note that experimental

data on the rates of hydrolysis and biodegradation are not known, so predicted values based on QSARs are applied. These indicated half-lives in the order of weeks to months.

Modeled concentrations of clarithromycin compared moderately well with laboratory analyses of environmental samples: the predicted values are lower than the measured concentrations that are below the LOD (Table 4).

- 0–0.03 ng/L modeled and <10 ng/L observed for the sea water,
- 0–0.01 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW modeled and <2.6 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW observed for the sediments, and
- 0–40 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW modeled and <0.04–0.62 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW observed for biota

3.2.4. Citalopram

Citalopram has a partitioning coefficient $\text{Log } K_{OW}$ of 3.5 which is comparable to that of clarithromycin (above). This implies partitioning to sediments and particulate matter, but unlike benzotriazole (with a lower $\text{Log } K_{OW}$ of 1.3), citalopram has a lower capacity for resuspension (or dissolution) into the water phase once bound to sediments. Hydrolysis of citalopram is not expected under normal environmental

Fig. 11. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of citalopram at the Sediment-Water Interface SWI during the 21-year scenario. Where C_{tot_diss} (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, C_{tot_part} (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, C_{in_biota} ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{tot_hydrolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{tot_photolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{tot_biodegrad}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $3 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 3100$, $K_H = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_P = 0.024 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The vertical distribution is presented as described in Fig. 5.

Fig. 12. Seasonal and interannual changes of citalopram during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved citalopram, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound citalopram. Constant injection with a rate of $3 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 3100$, $K_H = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_P = 0.024 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.00693 \text{ d}^{-1}$.

conditions, so removal of this substance from the modeled system is dominated by photolysis (half-life of approximately 28 days) and biodegradation (half-life on the order of weeks to months). The rate of photolysis is the largest differentiator between citalopram and clarithromycin. Citalopram has a longer half-life so is able to distribute in the water column, while clarithromycin undergoes rapid photolysis according to the model and the dissolved concentrations in the water column are lower.

Modeled concentrations of citalopram compared very well with laboratory analyses of environmental samples (Table 4) (see Fig. 11, Fig. 12).

- 0–0.01 ng/L modeled and less than all detection limits in analyses of sea water,
- 0–1 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ modeled <1.5–0.4 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ observed for the sediments, and
- 0–20 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ modeled and <0.1–1.0 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ observed for biota

3.2.5. Tributylphosphate

Tributylphosphate is moderately lipophilic ($\text{Log } K_{OW} 4$). Removal of this substance from the system is expected to be dominated by biodegradation as this is by far the fastest route. The half-life for biodegradation is reported as <7 days, compared to 11 years for hydrolysis. Photolysis is not expected for this compound. Modeled concentrations of tributylphosphate compared well with laboratory analyses (Table 4) (see Fig. 13, Fig. 14).

- 0–0.3 ng/L modeled and 5.6–42.0 ng/L observed in analyses of sea water,
- 0–100 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ modeled and 0.1–532 $\mu\text{g/kg DW}$ observed for the sediments, and
- 0–2000 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ modeled and 0.02–737 $\mu\text{g/kg WW}$ observed for analyses of biota

3.2.6. Teflubenzuron

Teflubenzuron is a lipophilic substance ($\text{Log } K_{OW} 5$) which binds to sediments and OM. It is regarded as persistent in the marine environment with a documented half-life in sediments of 170 days (Table 2).

Fig. 13. Seasonal and interannual changes of tributylphosphate during the 21-year scenario. Where $C_{i_tot_diss}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, $C_{i_tot_part}$ (ng L^{-1}) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, $C_{i_in_biota}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{i_tot_hydrolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{i_tot_photolysis}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{i_tot_biodegrad}$ ($\text{ng L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $95 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (marked with red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{ow} = 10000$, $K_H = 0.00019 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_p = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.099 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The vertical distribution is presented as described in Fig. 5.

Fig. 14. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of tributylphosphate (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) at SWI during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved tributylphosphate, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound tributylphosphate. Constant injection with a rate of $95 \mu\text{g/s}$ in the period 2015–2025 (marked with red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{ow} = 10000$, $K_H = 0.00019 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_p = 0 \text{ d}^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.099 \text{ d}^{-1}$.

It is expected to partition to OM and sediments where it will remain for many years. Remobilization to the water phase from the sediment layer is expected to be limited due to high lipophilicity (see Fig. 15, Fig. 16).

Modeled concentrations of teflubenzuron and laboratory analyses both demonstrate low concentrations of free teflubenzuron in the water phase. The compound is expected in particulate matter and sediments. Note that the model predicts higher concentrations in biota than have been observed in environmental samples, but there is limited measured data (Table 4).

- 0–0.2 ng/L modeled and <1.0–12.9 ng/L observed for the sea water,
- 0–500 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW modeled and <0.05–269 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ DW observed for the sediments, and
- 0–5000 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW modeled and <0.2–186 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ WW observed for biota

3.2.7. Potential effects of increasing temperature due to climate change

Climate change can affect the fate of substances in marine environments. For example, increasing temperatures may accelerate photolysis and biodegradation rates, which will affect the distribution of substances susceptible to this, such as clarithromycin and tributylphosphate. Increased sediment resuspension caused by more frequent and intense storm events may increase the bioavailability of lipophilic substances like octocrylene and teflubenzuron, which may increase exposure to marine organisms. Ocean acidification may also affect the partitioning of ionizable substances with a pKa at or near the pH of marine environments. The trend expected for such substances would be for acidic compounds to become more lipophilic (LogD increases), and basic substances to become more hydrophilic (LogD decreases). Generally, the indirect effects of climate change, i.e., increased precipitation and runoff, freshwater input that can change emission to coastal areas, can be studied in the frames of a 3-dimensional model resolving changes in several decade scales. However, for the purpose of this study, we can focus purely on changes in temperature as a demonstration of how this model may be applied to assess future climate risks or impacts.

Fig. 15. Seasonal and interannual changes of teflubenzuron during the 21-year scenario. Where C_{tot_diss} ($ng L^{-1}$) is the concentration in the sea water of dissolved contaminant, C_{tot_part} ($ng L^{-1}$) is the concentration in the sea water of particulate contaminant, C_{in_biota} ($\mu g kg^{-1}$) is the contaminant concentration in biota, $C_{tot_hydrolysis}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of hydrolysis, $C_{tot_photolysis}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of photolysis, $C_{tot_biodegrad}$ ($ng L^{-1} d^{-1}$) is the rate of biodegradation. Constant injection with a rate of $50 \mu g/s$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 100000$, $K_H = 0.023 d^{-1}$, $K_P = 0.035 d^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.0041 d^{-1}$. The vertical distribution is presented as described in Fig. 5.

Fig. 16. Seasonal and interannual changes of fluxes of teflubenzuron (in $\mu g m^{-2} d^{-1}$) at SWI during the 21-year scenario. The upper plot shows the flux of dissolved teflubenzuron, while the lower plot shows the flux of particle-bound teflubenzuron. Constant injection with a rate of $50 \mu g/s$ in the period 2015–2025 (bounded by red lines), followed by a recovery period after 2025. $K_{OW} = 100000$, $K_H = 0.023 d^{-1}$, $K_P = 0.035 d^{-1}$, $K_d = 0.0041 d^{-1}$.

Globally, sea surface temperature (SST) increased by approximately $0.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ between 1980 and 2020 (Venegas et al., 2023). Observations of the upper (0–700 m) near-global ocean (60° N – 60° S) show a past warming rate of $0.15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ per decade (1993–2019), accelerating to $0.280 \pm 0.068 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the last decade (2010–2019; Garcia-Soto et al. (2021)). Depending on emissions scenarios, the mean global SST is projected to increase by 0.86 – $2.89 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (between 1995–2014 and 2081–2100; Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2021)). However, it is worth noting that the global mean change does not capture the regional variability that expected, for example due to changes in ocean circulation, or local air–sea fluxes (e.g., due to changes in sea ice cover).

The aim of this study is to demonstrate how the model may be used for future applications. Therefore, given the uncertainty in representing regional processes within global models, here two scenarios are considered with temperature increased by either 1.5 or $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This idealized approach considers a uniform temperature increase throughout the

water column, with no assumption made on how stratification may change in the region.

In case of an increased temperature in the Oslofjord, benzotriazole concentrations, as an example, are predicted to change (Fig. 17). If the temperature remains at $6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the Oslofjord, the highest concentration of benzotriazole is expected to be around $600 \mu g/m^3$, with concentrations approaching $0 \mu g/m^3$ around 2030 if a pollution cessation in 2024 would be modeled. For a $1.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increase in temperature, the peak concentration is expected to be around $550 \mu g/m^3$, with concentrations approaching $0 \mu g/m^3$ around 2029. With a $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increase, the peak concentration is expected to be around $400 \mu g/m^3$, and concentrations will approach $0 \mu g/m^3$ around 2027.

4. Discussion

This work aimed to elaborate a model for analyzing the fate of CECs in the marine environment. The model application set out to

Fig. 17. Integrated concentrations of benzotriazole in case of current temperature (top), increase of 1.5 °C (middle), and increase of 5 °C (bottom) in the Oslofjord. The red lines indicates the injection period 2015–2025 of the contaminants.

explain how compound-specific properties and seasonally varying biogeochemistry determine the fate of six illustrative contaminants of emerging concern (iCECs) in the Oslofjord. Across compounds, three robust patterns emerged: (i) the “biological pump” continually redistributes contaminants from surface waters to depth, producing marked seasonal cycles in the dissolved phase; (ii) sediments behave as both a sink and a delayed secondary source, with upward diffusive fluxes of the dissolved phase persisting after inputs cease; and (iii) persistence in the water column and in sediments is primarily governed by the balance between hydrophobic partitioning (approximated here by K_{OW}) and the effective first-order loss pathways (photolysis, hydrolysis, biodegradation) under local light, redox and temperature regimes. These behaviors are internally consistent across the scenario years and align, in first order, with the available environmental observations used for calibration.

4.1. Model development

Our integrated approach (combining 2DBP, BROM, and a CEC transformation module) advances previous fugacity-based models (e.g., Breivik et al. 2004) by explicitly resolving seasonal OM dynamics and redox-dependent degradation. This is critical for accurately simulating CEC fluxes at the sediment-water interface, a process often oversimplified in multimedia fate models. The 1-dimensional benthic-pelagic model applied in this study allowed us to analyze the fate of the contaminants in a simplified system, with a source of pollution in the upper part of the water column and a possibility of its transport to the sediments below. In reality, the source of the substance may be far removed from the place of its accumulation at the bottom. To be able to predict the wider spatial distribution and fate of contaminants over time, it will be necessary to use 3-dimensional models. The model developed for this study, a FABM-family module for contaminant transformation, can be used with other hydrodynamical and biogeochemical models. Such application of this model is planned for future work, to support wider monitoring and observation in case study regions. The contaminant transformation module developed here considers influence of light, temperature, living and dead organic matter, pH and redox, and can be used for polar and non polar substances, and model predicted pH and redox can be efficiently used. From a modeling standpoint, embedding the contaminants module in a 3-D hydrodynamic host would allow explicit treatment of lateral advection, near-field dilution, bathymetric controls on exchange and episodic events—key for evaluating local measures and for attributing observed spatial heterogeneity. Introducing explicit particle size/quality, sorption kinetics (rather than instantaneous equilibrium), and potential redox-dependent biodegradation in sediments would better capture

benthic processing and the timing/magnitude of legacy fluxes. With the addition of a 3-dimensional model it will be possible to study the effects of spatial changes in the release of contaminants, as well as further climate-related changes, e.g., increasing runoff, marine heat waves, deoxygenation.

4.2. Agreement with observations and sources of mismatch

Across matrices, modeled concentrations generally fall within observed ranges used for calibration, particularly for benzotriazole, citalopram, octocrylene and teflubenzuron. Some mismatches—such as low modeled tributylphosphate in seawater relative to reported concentrations—likely reflect (i) our deliberately simplified source representation (constant upper-layer input distributed over a broad area), which omits short-term variability, storm-driven runoff pulses and near-field gradients; (ii) uncertainties in literature-based rate constants (e.g., tributylphosphate hydrolysis/biodegradation spanning orders of magnitude); and (iii) the use of K_{OW} as a proxy for sorption to diverse OM pools. The latter is especially pertinent for ionizable organics (e.g., clarithromycin, citalopram, benzotriazole), for which the environmentally relevant distribution depends on pH and can deviate from neutral K_{OW} .

A further limitation is the one-dimensional (vertical) configuration. While this is appropriate for diagnosing vertical exchanges and the benthic-pelagic coupling that dominate our questions, it neglects lateral advection and turbulence, lateral gradients around outfalls, and episodic intrusions of different water masses—all processes that can structure concentration fields at management-relevant scales. Finally, photolysis was parameterized with simple first-order rates; apparent photolysis in natural waters depends on spectral irradiance, water optics and dissolved constituents (e.g., CDOM) that can differ seasonally and spatially. For octocrylene, for instance, reported photostability in some studies (Anstöter et al., 2023; Kockler et al., 2012; Cowden et al., 2023) would, if adopted, increase the predicted sediment burden and prolong recovery.

These caveats argue for cautious interpretation of absolute magnitudes while giving confidence in the qualitative process rankings, the direction of seasonal signals and the relative ordering of persistence among compounds — features the model reproduces consistently and that are most useful for screening-level management decisions.

4.3. Process controls on contrasting iCEC behaviors

The substances investigated have different fates in the marine environment, mainly dependent on the iCEC physicochemical properties. The suite of iCECs spans two practical endmembers. Benzotriazole, with low hydrophobicity, remains largely in the dissolved phase, shows

strong seasonal drawdown during periods of high organic matter production, and responds quickly to changes in inputs. Its concentrations in surface waters are therefore sensitive to both biological seasonality and photolytic loss. At the opposite end, octocrylene and teflubenzuron partition strongly into POM/biota and sediments. Their dissolved concentrations in the water column are low, but their particulate and sediment inventories accumulate during input years and decline only slowly thereafter. For such compounds, the bottom flux reverses after inputs cease: downward particulate fluxes collapse while small but persistent upward diffusive fluxes of the dissolved fraction continue from contaminated surface sediments. Citalopram and clarithromycin illustrate the role of loss processes: despite similar hydrophobicity ($\text{Log } K_{OW}$ 3–3.5), clarithromycin's rapid photolysis in illuminated layers depletes the dissolved pool quickly, whereas citalopram's slower photolysis permits broader water-column distribution before removal. Tributylphosphate represents a biodegradation-dominated compound: even with moderate hydrophobicity, its short biodegradation half-life confines persistence mainly to periods close to sources. Compounds with low or moderate lipophilicity, such as benzotriazole or citalopram and clarithromycin, are more mobile in the water column (Arp and Hale, 2022). Substances with shorter half-lives in the environment are less susceptible to slower processes such as sediment burial and resuspension. Clarithromycin, for example, is expected to undergo rapid photolysis, which reduces concentrations in the water column (Rodríguez-López et al., 2021a). A key implication is that the seasonal “cleansing” of surface waters during productive months—caused by partitioning to sinking particles—should not be misinterpreted as true removal from the system. Instead, it represents redistribution to benthic compartments, with potential exposure implications for sediment-dwelling biota and for benthic-pelagic coupling during resuspension events. Equally, the model indicates that a potential management action that stops inputs will be followed by compound-specific recovery trajectories: rapid for mobile/photolabile species, and protracted for hydrophobic, slowly degrading species, as was found experimentally for PFAS (Evich et al., 2022), DDTs (Zeng and Venkatesan, 1999) and several other POPs (Nyberg et al., 2015).

4.4. Sediments as delayed sources and management relevance

The predicted post-cessation upward fluxes at the SWI generalize a well-known legacy effect for hydrophobic organics: sediments act as integrators of historical inputs and subsequently as weak, long-lived sources to near-bottom waters (Achman et al., 1996; Fernandez et al., 2014; Eek et al., 2008). The strength and duration of this “legacy leak” vary with the compound and with the effectiveness of burial. In our simulations, octocrylene and teflubenzuron show the longest benthic residence, reflecting strong partitioning and comparatively slow net loss. From a management perspective, two consequences follow. First, reductions of the contaminants' discharges should yield near-immediate improvements for mobile iCECs in surface waters (e.g., benzotriazole), but not necessarily for benthic compartments or for highly lipophilic compounds. Second, for compounds with large sediment inventories, complementary benthic risk management (e.g., minimizing resuspension, considering local capping where appropriate) may be required to accelerate recovery.

4.5. Climate sensitivity and future exposure

A main strength of modeling approaches is the ability to predict future scenarios, such as the impact of climate change on the fate of CECs. The projected scenarios presented here demonstrate how the model may be used to investigate impacts of increased temperature on fate of contaminants. However, there is scope for the model to be used with further climate projections, targeted for regions of interest and including impacts of wider environmental change. Temperature, pH, and hydrodynamics may all change under future climate scenarios,

altering concentrations and impacts of pollution. It is then important for policy that trends in pollution and ecosystem health can be predicted to allow for ecosystem-based, long-term marine management. The temperature perturbation experiments illustrate how warming can reshape fate by accelerating biologically mediated and temperature-dependent losses. For the benzotriazole test case, warming shortened the time to near-zero integrated inventories by several years and reduced peak burdens. Similar to the modeled here tendencies would be expected for other compounds where photolysis/biodegradation dominate. However, warming also co-varies with changes in stratification, deoxygenation, storminess and pH—factors that could counteract or amplify simple temperature effects. For example, more frequent storms could increase sediment resuspension and transiently elevate bioavailability of hydrophobic compounds (Eggleton and Thomas, 2004; Dong et al., 2016); progressive acidification (Feely et al., 2016) will alter ionization and thus $\text{Log } K_{OW}$ for bases and acids. While these coupled impacts are beyond the scope of the present 1-D sensitivity, the framework demonstrated here is readily extensible to test such compound- and scenario-specific hypotheses. This study provides a first demonstration of modeling CECs fate in the marine environment. In summary, the novelty of the applied model lies in its coupled, mechanistic representation of compound-specific loss pathways, the biological pump, and benthic-pelagic exchanges, which together govern the persistence and compartmental distribution of iCECs in marine systems. This integrated framework enables transparent, process-based screening of management options—such as sediment remediation, seasonal alignment of monitoring with phytoplankton blooms, and climate-resilient regulatory adaptations—thereby advancing beyond simpler one-dimensional approaches and addressing the previously limited understanding of CECs dynamics in marine environments.

5. Conclusions

Despite its simplifying assumptions, the present framework already supports actionable screening:

- **Sediment as a Long-Term Sink:** The prolonged release of CECs from sediments post-emission cessation implies that traditional water-focused remediation (e.g., WWTP upgrades) may be insufficient. Sediment capping or monitored natural recovery (MNR) could be evaluated using this model.
- **Seasonal Monitoring Strategies:** Given the strong influence of phytoplankton blooms on CEC cycling, monitoring programs should align with seasonal OM production to capture peak contamination phases.
- **Climate Adaptation:** Warming may reduce the persistence of some CECs but could also increase the bioavailability of sediment-stored pollutants. Regulatory frameworks should incorporate climate resilience into CEC management.

In sum, the biological pump, benthic-pelagic exchanges and compound-specific loss pathways jointly govern iCEC persistence and exposure in the Oslofjord. By resolving these mechanisms in a coupled, mechanistic way and reproducing the principal seasonal and compartmental patterns observed to date, the model provides a transparent basis for prioritizing management actions and for designing the next generation of monitoring and process studies. It should also be noted that studies on CECs have only emerged relatively recently, and consequently there is still limited information on their distribution and variability in the marine environment. The availability of new observational data will enable more rigorous model validation and contribute to improving the robustness and reliability of the modeling framework. In particular, the use of three-dimensional models instead of one-dimensional approaches in future work will help overcome current limitations and allow for more comprehensive and reliable interpretations of the results.

Fig. B.18. Seasonal dynamics of the biogeochemical model components: PHY, Het, DOM and POM (in μM N) during 30 years. The upper plots show the vertical distribution in the 90-meter water column, and the bottom plots show distributions at the Sediment-Water Interface (SWI), with 10 cm in bottom water and 10 cm in the sediment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evgeniy Yakushev: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Malcolm Reid:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anfisa Berezina:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Shamil Yakubov:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **André Staalstrøm:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Maria Austrheim:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jennifer Graham:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Bavo De Witte:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ian Alan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Samantha Martins:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Steven Brooks:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

In writing this work, the authors employed ChatGPT to organize an initial draft of the Discussion. After using this, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Conversion from volumetric to weight units in the sediments

The model's concentration units are expressed in weight (g) or quantity (mol) in volume (L or m^3) of water or sediment. To compare the concentrations in the sediment with the observations, which are expressed as dry weight (DW) of sediment, a conversion was needed. According to the NIVA experimental work, the ratio between the sediment DW and wet weight (WW) is $\text{DW}/\text{WW} = 0.6$. If we assume the DW sediment density is 6 g/ml, and the water density is 1 g/ml, that will give us the total volume for 1 g of WW: $0.6 \text{ g DW}/6 \text{ g/ml} + 0.4 \text{ g water}/1 \text{ g/ml} = 0.1 \text{ ml} + 0.4 \text{ ml} = 0.5 \text{ ml}$. So, 0.1 ml of DW corresponds to 0.5 of total volume (DW+water) and the ratio should be: Dry matter / (Dry matter + water) = 0.2, which will give sediment density (as WW) 2 g/ml. This value corresponds well to the density of the wet Oslofjord sediments measured by using sound speed: 1.4 to 2.3 g/ml (Eidem and Kolstrup, 2022).

Appendix B. Modeling of the Oslo fjord biogeochemistry.

Here we show supplementary figures for the application of BROM-2DBP model to the Oslofjord. The absence of interannual changes of biogeochemical characteristics in the end of the spinup period is shown in Fig. B.18.

A comparison of the modeled and observed vertical distributions is shown in Fig. B.19.

The model predicted vertical distributions in the water column and the upper sediments for March are shown in Fig. B.20.

Seasonal variabilities of the model variables are shown in Fig. 4. These variabilities were taken as a baseline for the iCECs modeling.

Data availability

No data were produced as part of this work. The code of the model is available on GitHub (https://github.com/BottomRedoxModel/BROM/tree/master/brom/brom_partit.F90) and can be used in modeling efforts related to CEC transformation.

Fig. B.19. Vertical distributions in the water column of the modeled (lines) and observed (marks) seasonal variability of vertical distributions of O₂, SiO₂, PO₄, and NO₃ for summer (orange) and winter (blue) periods.

Fig. B.20. Modeled vertical distribution of the model parameters in the water column (top) and the SWI (Bottom) for March.

Fig. B.21. Modeled seasonal variability in the Oslo fjord of the selected variables of the model BROM: Mn4 - particulate quadrivalent manganese, Fe3 - particulate trivalent iron, pH - pH in total scale, Mn2 - dissolved bivalent manganese, Fe2 - dissolved bivalent iron, H2S - hydrogen sulfide (Yakushev et al., 2017). The upper plots show the vertical distribution in the 90-meter water column, and the bottom plots show distributions at SWI, with 10 cm in bottom water and 10 cm in the sediment.

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